

BILINGUALISM AND MULTILINGUALISM IN MODERN SOCIETY

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Annotation: *The modern world necessitates the knowledge of at least one foreign language, given the changes that have occurred in our society in recent years (increased scientific, business, and cultural contacts, the spread of mass media, and a massive amount of scientific and technical information), all of which require the knowledge of foreign languages.*

Keywords: *bilingualism, multilingualism, native language, communication, society*

Bilingualism has become a reality in our day due to the existence of bilingual states, globalization tendencies, and an increase in the number of people who speak multiple languages at the same time. As a result, not only from the position of linguistics, but also from the perspectives of philosophy, psychology, sociology, and even physiology, the phenomenon known as bilingualism is of great interest. Any multinational state is impossible to exist without bilingualism or multilingualism because living in the same community necessitates the presence of a language as a means of communication (in addition to the native language), which would serve as a foundation for mutual understanding among members of a multinational society over a long period of its socio-economic development. Bilingualism is important for any community because it allows representatives of different nations to coordinate their actions in the workplace and social activities. It does not need fluency in both languages.

The processes that started at the end of the twentieth century are still going from strength to strength in the twenty-first century, and they represent a new stage in the evolution of modern civilization. International relations are rapidly increasing, resulting in intimate interaction between different cultures and civilizations. There are only a few places left on the planet where residents are exposed to one language throughout their lives: their native languages. Television, mass media, and the Internet, as well as foreign language forms of communication, are pervasive. Without tourism and migration, the modern world would be unimaginable, and it is now impossible to develop without some understanding of foreign languages.

A multicultural, multilingual individual is a caretaker of cultural legacy and an intermediary between many peoples and ethnic groups in the age of globalization. As a result of current technology and society's informatization, the demand for professionals in various areas of economics, industry, and research grows, leading to

bilingualism and multilingualism. The languages of more numerous and technically dominant peoples predominate in the information space. As a result, language domination substantially aids the process of imparting their views and values to the peoples and states they control, as well as other peoples' cultures and ideologies. Globalization causes a considerable shift toward direct communication, both between institutions and between individuals; this is what drives the expansion of global social bilingualism, which is characterized by continual growth in terms of both population coverage and language competency. Anyone can be nominated for the role of a single language of international communication, but this does not imply that all languages are eligible.

The language of interethnic communication is singled out as a result of the expansion of direct communication, and the major form of bilingualism is established on its foundation. This process, which is driven by modern society's requirements, is one of the principles governing the evolution of information civilisation.

Individual countries are affected in two ways by globalization. On the one hand, numerous obstacles between individuals are being removed, including language limitations, which impede cultural and national interpenetration and mixing. The framework allows each ethnic group to maintain its identity and distinctiveness, resulting in a wide range of cultures and nationalities around the world. However, there is currently constant cultural interaction, with cultures from many ethnic groups dispersed around the world. However, there is also cultural imposition from one country to another. In this sense, we might discuss the reversal of globalization: an increase in people's interest in their ancestors and roots. It becomes important to know your people's history and culture and to maintain it by passing it on to future generations so that the ethnos do not disappear.

The ability of certain segments of the population to communicate in two languages is referred to as bilingualism. Being bilingual involves belonging to two separate social groups at the same time because language is a function of social groupings. Mixed marriages have more complicated connections. In such situations, children frequently speak two-family languages: one with their father and the other with their mother. Cultural diffusion happens when concepts and ideas regarding specific phenomena, items created by nature, human hands or industry, technical processes, conventions and rituals, and much more are borrowed. There is the creation of words designating the above things and notions at the same time as cultural borrowings, which are imprinted in culture.

Since social factors are the primary causes of bilingualism, the strengthening of economic and cultural connections between states leads to a rise in the number of bilingual (or multilingual) citizens. Many instances can be used to demonstrate this point. Individual bilingualism typically develops with limited cultural exchanges, which should be noted among them. When the contacts are more numerous and active, group or mass bilingualism is more likely to emerge. This typically occurs during

large-ethnic-group migrations, when numerous ethnic communities cohabit inside the framework of a state association, and when neighbouring states engage in active engagement. Earlier, such bilingualism was highly common throughout the conquests of other peoples.

Conclusion

As a result of the modern world's complexity and mobility, language processes have a multi-vector direction: from language disappearance to eventual bilingualism and multilingualism.

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